

A Cloud Architecture for Emotion Recognition in Human-Robot Interaction Based on the Appraisal Theory

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Abstract—This work proposes a cloud system, structured as a set of REST API endpoints, for online human emotion recognition in spontaneous human-robot verbal interaction. Based on the appraisal theory of emotion, the system acquires data about the person's expected appraisal of a given situation, depending on their needs and goals, and combines it with sensory data, such as facial expressions, angles of the head, and gaze of the person, and distance between the person and the robot. The whole set of data is used to infer the emotional state of the person during the interaction through a Random Forest classifier, trained for binary classification (i.e., positive vs. negative emotions). Results confirmed that using both sources of data led to a performance improvement both in the K-fold and in the Leave One Person Out scenarios.

Index Terms—Human-robot interaction, social robotics, cloud robotics, REST API, emotion recognition, appraisal theory

I. INTRODUCTION

Providing a natural, genuine and effective human-robot interaction (HRI) represents one of the major and fascinating challenges in the field of Social Robotics [1]. The most crucial skill that confers naturalism to interactions between humans is our ability to infer the emotional states of others based on non-verbal signals, such as facial expressions, voice, body posture and movement [2]. This allows us to adjust our social behaviors and communication patterns to grant the optimization of the interaction. A social robot with the same ability would be able to reliably adapt to changes in their partners' behavior, and earn their trust during the interaction.

The vast literature on emotion recognition covers (i) the problem of emotion classification, discussing how emotions should be represented, and (ii) the choice of the most informative non-verbal signals for the robot to acquire and interpret. In other words, the two main research topics establish the output and the input of the classification process, respectively.

Narrowing it down to social robotics, most previous studies performed emotion recognition by combining multiple sensory modalities, such as facial expression, body posture, and speech, using them with black-box models to predict an emotion from a list of possible labels [3]–[5].

This approach only considers emotional expressions, as people reveal them to the outside world, voluntarily or not [6]. However, emotional expressions do not necessarily reflect

the emotional state of the person [7], which can be expressed in different ways depending on several individual factors, or even hidden. For this reason, these techniques lead to good classification performances in acted situations but are less suitable in actual HRI scenarios.

This work proposes a novel emotion recognition framework, able to assess the emotional state of the person during a dyadic autonomous HRI.

II. EMOTION RECOGNITION THROUGH COGNITIVE APPRAISAL

The proposed emotion recognition framework is based on an implementation of the appraisal theory of emotion [8]. According to the theory, emotions are the result of a two-dimension individual evaluation of the situation that a person is in: in the primary appraisal, the person evaluates the situation in terms of relevance to their needs and congruence with their goals, while the secondary appraisal mainly concerns the person's possibilities to cope with the situation. In a previous study [9], the system was used to collect data from participants who had a spontaneous and autonomous verbal interaction with the humanoid robot Pepper, programmed to elicit different emotions in various moments of the conversation. Throughout the interaction, information about the appraisal of the person was combined with state-of-the-art sensory data. Then, the collected data were used to train a Random Forest classifier. Binary classification (i.e., positive vs. negative emotion) results showed that using both sources of data led to a performance improvement compared to the use of sensory data only, both in the K-fold and in the Leave One Person Out (LOPO) scenarios.

III. CLOUD ARCHITECTURE FOR EMOTION RECOGNITION

Given these preliminary results, the current work proposes a cloud architecture for online implementation of the system. The system is fully integrated with the CAIR interaction system [10], able to manage a knowledge-based autonomous interaction, by accepting commands to execute actions and conversing with the person about a variety of topics. It is based on a client-server architecture and it can be used by most devices with Internet connectivity, able to acquire an input through a microphone and provide an output through a screen or speaker, combined with a camera (and possibly other sensors) acquiring data from the environment. Services are based on the use of REST APIs [11], which grant flexibility, scalability, portability and independence.

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Figure 1 shows the overall architecture of the system.

Fig. 1. Emotion recognition framework.

A. Server

The server is composed of dialogue and emotion recognition web services. They are implemented as REST APIs using Python¹. This choice allows the system to be easily expandable by adding new services, if necessary.

The dialogue service is mainly responsible for managing HRI. It recognizes the person’s intention to discuss a specific topic or to ask the agent to execute a task. By exploiting the Ontology [10] (containing all concepts and sentences used in the interaction), it provides a response to the agent, which contains the verbal reply or the specific task to execute, and the updated client state. The latter includes dialogue information, e.g., the current topic of conversation and the type of sentence chosen by the system, and is also used to store the emotional state of the person. In order to get the emotion label, it makes requests to the emotion recognition service once it has processed the user sentence, used to compute the appraisal data. These, as previously introduced in Section II, encode information about the person’s needs and goals and how coherent they are with what the robot says and does.

The Emotion recognition service exploits the pre-trained Random Forest classifier to assess the emotional state of the user. Moreover, upon request from the client, it starts and stops a “Sensory data processing” task that processes data coming from sensors through the cloud, which is then used for model inference. For example, it is able to extract information

¹The Flask-RESTful framework was used to develop the web services - <https://flask-restful.readthedocs.io/en/latest/>

about the user’s facial expressions, head and gaze angles, and the distance from the camera, but new functionalities may be added to exploit other sources of sensory data. Post-processed data are continuously stored in a database, where they are joined to the corresponding appraisal data coming from the dialogue service.

As for the aim of this study, the client represents the robot (or, more generically, the agent) used for the interaction. However, the client may also be a computer or in general most devices with Internet connectivity, able to acquire an input through a microphone and provide an output through a screen or speaker. Each client is associated with a state, which is initialized at the first request to the Dialogue service and is then stored locally. From the client side, the state is updated to contain useful information, such as the two moments when the person and the robot started speaking, respectively. These pieces of information are then used by the Dialogue and the Emotion Recognition services to provide the response.

Moreover, the client also makes requests to the Emotion Recognition service, to start the acquisition from one or multiple sensors. As for the camera, it provides the IP address of the video stream.

B. Sensory Devices

Sensory devices acquire data and stream them to the Cloud. Although so far the post-processing algorithm has been designed to extract data from camera video streams only, in principle the system may be used for other types of sensors, such as a smartwatch or a microphone for speech emotion recognition.

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